

1 **Axonal guidance receptors are active in the human embryo prior to development of the CNS in the**
2 **trophectoderm.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of axonal
9 guidance receptors as lineage commitment cooperating factors in embryonic stem cells of the human
10 embryo. *Sliitrk3* and *Ephb3* were essential and basic components of the TE commitment signature.
11 The data indicate a broader function for axonal guidance receptors and the repulsive or attractive cues
12 associated with their combinatorial functions and interaction, in orchestration of complex differentiation
13 processes.

14 Citations

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